

Can Pro Wrestling Explain The 2024 Election War Games?

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ABSTRACT

As we head into the upcoming turbulence of the 2024 United States Election, there is an uncanny resemblance in the tactics used in the approach leading up to the election and those used in the sport entertainment of Pro Wrestling. Elements of both entertainment and “angertainment” are equally intertwined and designed to captivate legions of followers and voters. The goal being to create a façade where it is no longer possible to decipher reality from fantasy; emotional triggers that will determine the future versus what is in the best interest of the voting public.

This article will address how both “sports entertainment” arenas intersect, each with a similar design to one another and intended to achieve the “desired results” long before the actual event. The key “actors” in this event: Donald Trump and Vincent McMahon.

Professional wrestling has, to some extent, been explored, but it is the visual medium of television where to its loyal followers, it shines. More importantly, the role of television has illustrated their larger-than-life personalities. This phenomenon of Donald Trump is well documented in both entertainment as well as academic journals, but it is also through television where Donald Trump was able to revive a sagging career through “The Apprentice” which set the path and more importantly, the “tone” towards the PR exposure required for his Presidential run in 2016.

Much has been written about the Trump phenomenon. Specifically, the objective of playing the ratings games and “click bait” but as the world inches closer to the 2024 election and the threat of fascism being dangled before the American people, examining the tactics and approaches being used is more important than ever. The tactics used in the Pro Wrestling world can offer an insight that once examined may help to provide a clear picture of the “end game” long before it happens.

The results focus on the early origins of the “good guys/bad guys”, negative campaigns, the concept of retribution and revenge for previous matches to Trump’s threats of his plans once he wins. Both men have been involved in payouts due to lawsuits, hush money and sexual assault and are perceived or self-promoted as creative businessmen who have shrewdly integrated politics and

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world events into their characters and business. Finally, the flirtation with Fascism and Nazism they both employ into policies, politics and entertainment. The ultimate connection between these two, their 1984 WrestleMania, and the follow-up where Vincent Mc Mahon challenged Trump to a match at WrestleMania 23 in 2007 billed as 'the battle of the billionaires. Understanding the commonalities is crucial as we head into the ultimate match, the 2024 Election where if the courts rule in his Favour and he is allowed to run, Trump will face off against the “good guy”, Joe Biden in a battle of good vs. evil and where democracy could be the real loser with no rematch.

KEYWORDS: political, sports entertainment, upper mobility, public perception, ethics, anarchy, democracy.

WHERE IT ALL STARTED

As a kid growing up my dad surreptitiously aroused my curiosity in watching this “weird & exciting” sort of sport-pro wrestling viewed on our black and white 10” TV. He wouldn’t let me change the channel. Some neighbors even asked to come over for the 2 events during the week because we had the only TV in the immediate neighborhood. Today as a long-time fan, I still watch it at times and it’s consistent. Still a good guy (baby faces) and a bad guy (heels) who happens to win via vicarious often supernatural means disappointing me again. However, today’s political world is not the scripted show I marveled at but has some remarkable similarities. There is a real match that still demonstrates the unfairness I remembered and still programmed with potential deadly outcomes. This is the essence of this article examining how both “sports” intersect and have a similar design to get results before the event ever happens. To be fair, the essence of this undertaking will be on the “heels” who make the matches interesting and then disappointing to the fans (voters) rather than the “baby faces” who seem to have it won then-run out of gimmicks and lose. For the script Donald Trump takes the persona of the bad guys and the good guys are closer to the Joe Biden character.

While my loyalty to wrestling has continued, I was a latecomer to politics. I watched the news lightly but was riveted by the following event 20 years ago. The keynote address at the 2004 Democratic National Convention (DNC) was given by the Illinois State Senator, United States senatorial candidate, and future President Barack Obama on the night of Tuesday, July 27, 2004, in Boston, Massachusetts. His unexpected landslide victory in the March 2004 Illinois U.S. Senate Democratic primary made him a rising star within the national Democratic Party overnight. His keynote address was well received, which further elevated his status within the Democratic Party. Stepping on stage shortly before 9:45 pm EDT to the 1964 song, "Keep on Pushing" by The Impressions, Obama would go on to speak for 17 minutes, interrupted 33 times by the audience's applause. I knew who the next “heavyweight champion” of the US would be. (Barack Obama, Wikipedia, January 2024).

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That was the lightening rod that tweaked my heightened curiosity and now nightly obsession to politics-the other aspect of this article. However, it is critical to present my personal feelings concerning the players in this article to maintain fairness. In the beginning of my fascination with both the WWE and politics prior to the 2008 election, I was intrigued with and by the unique antics of both people running for President in 2024 highlighted in this work. However, as the 16 years have progressed, and I became more conversant and aware of the similar bravado my initial “let me watch this last interview on TV” changed to this: “Hold it-listen to what they just said “! Currently I needed to test my perceptions with this rejoinder. “Did I hear what I thought I just heard”? So, these two bigger than life personalities have significantly impacted on my current feelings of real world acceptability.

To make my need to have this article written clear, it is not an empirical article written by an academic but one written by an academic and fan of both sports who suddenly realized that there is a direct linkage as the big main event is nine months away. It was significant to question my perception at times “am I watching wrestling or politics...or both”? So, this writer has arrived at the crossroads between the two entities. The rhetoric is just too close to be coincidental.

ORIGINS OF PRO WRESTLING

Professional wrestling as a form of theater evolved out of the commonplace practice of match fixing among American wrestlers dating back to the mid 20th century. The public eventually caught on to the deception but came to accept professional wrestling as a performance art because they found wrestling to be more entertaining when faked. Collegiate wrestling is rather boring. Wrestlers responded by adding melodrama, gimmickry, and outlandish stunt work to their performances to further raise the entertainment levels. Nevertheless, they kept pretending the matches were real competitions, and the fans played along. This is a tradition known as kayfabe which is a shorthand term that involves acknowledging the staged, scripted nature of professional wrestling, as opposed to a competitive sport, despite being presented as authentic.

Some matches are designed to further the story of only one participant. It could be intended to portray an unstoppable force, a lucky underdog, a sore loser, or any other characterization. Some stories result from a natural rivalry. Outside of performance, these are referred to as feuds that can exist between any number of participants and can last from a few days to decades. (Professional Wrestling, Wikipedia, January 2024) (Donald Trump, Wikipedia, January 2024).

While pro wrestling is often described simplistically as a "soap opera for males", it has also been cited as filling the role of past forms of literature and theater; a synthesis of classical heroics, revenge tragedies, plays, even comedy and burlesque. The characters and storylines portrayed by a successful promotion are seen to reflect the current mood, attitudes, and concerns of that promotion's society and can in turn influence those same things. Wrestling's high levels of violence and masculinity make it a vicarious outlet for aggression during peacetime. However, it has also

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mirrored global feuds with potential enemies of the US such as wrestlers from Japan, Germany, Korea, Russia, Middle East to name a few challenged American heroes in the ring.

Similarly, political campaigns and ads that focus upon extreme negativity and fabricated non-events carefully crafted for the GOP campaigns are usually more exciting than those presenting the facts only as the Democrats do capturing the attention of many non-college and disenfranchised loyal followers in a similar way that pro wrestling has done forever. They do the “dirty stuff” very well.

THE CONUNDRUM: “ART IMITATING LIFE”?

Today I somehow see Wrestling and Politics in the same arena: “Sports Entertainment” where it’s difficult to separate “art imitating life” or vice-versa. In most matches as well as political warfare, there is a protagonist and then the antagonist. Usually the “good guy also the hero” (USA) is about to win but somehow loses by magical external interference (China or Russia) who always plays dirty but the referee is either distracted or legally blind and misses the low blow or some substance thrown into the eyes of the “baby face” and most times by another ally of the “heel” magically lurking outside of the ring who manages to help his confrere win at the last second again. Ah, disappointed again!

However, if and when the “baby face” wins then the “heel” screams (on a mic) during an interview that it was “rigged” and already demands a rematch which increases the interest and demand for “retribution” as well as a bigger financial gate in the next big show in person or PPV. It is now approved by the General Manager of the show who could be an Attorney General in politics leveraging her/his office to turn the results of the match or worse, election around under suspicious somewhat legal grounds often not found in the wrestling rulebooks (there are none) or in some article of the constitution that used be the guard rail for rationality. Somehow, I remember this script during the 2015 and 2020 elections previews. The 2024 campaign will undoubtedly be fought on the platform of “retribution “by the Trump camp and candidate himself”. If memories are correct, Trump claimed even before the 2016 election that if he lost, it could only happen by it being rigged a la wrestling. The scripts and previews are quite similar. So, stay tuned.

WRESTLING AND UPWARD MOBILITY

However pro wrestling as well as prime time TV has vaulted stars to higher level careers than ever conceived of. Look at the Rock-a.k.a. Rocky Johnson, who transformed his charismatic character in the ring to being the highest paid Hollywood star in action movies and continues to entertain in both venues. His fans are now clamoring for him to run in the 2028 election. Then there was Donald Trump who, at the lowest point in his scandal- laden career, segway into the 14-year running show, “The Apprentice” (2004-15) that many believe gave him the PR exposure to begin his run for the Presidency in 2016 that he was successful in. He often played the show character in

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his political rallies by shouting, “You’re fired” “to “Throw him *outta* here” when a non-fan disagreed with his many false campaign statements. Donald Trump was the show's host from the beginning. However, Trump was fired by NBC when the studio disagreed with remarks, he made about Mexican immigrants during his announcement that he was running for President of the United States on June 16, 2015. (Donald Trump, Wikipedia, January 2024). He did run on that. This set the tone for his whole presidential run that enthralled the disenfranchised always looking for a scapegoat... “angertainment.”

Currently, the largest professional wrestling company worldwide is the United States-based WWE, who magically bought out many smaller regional companies as well as primary competitors in the late 1980s. These often-nefarious deals were engineered by Vincent K. McMahon, a close business ally of Donald Trump, who today has amassed several billion dollars only to be ousted by the corporate board of his own creation for sexual harassment allegations and payoffs from corporate coffers that were deemed illegal leading to his removal after 50+ years in the game. Despite McMahon’s public embarrassments, the lord of Titan Towers remains beloved by fans around the world and plenty of industry journalists. This is critical in analyzing how Donald Trump has his followers and loyalists despite 91 indictments for multiple criminal charges. In the years to follow, many more allegedly shady dealings would come to light for McMahon, many of them detailed in the Wall Street Journal’s 2022 report that McMahon paid out \$12 million over the past 16 years to cover alleged accounts of sexual misconduct and infidelity a bombshell that resulted in McMahon temporarily stepping away from the organization. (Professional Wrestling, Wikipedia, January 2024) (World Wrestling Entertainment, Wikipedia, January 2024).

There appears to be a relationship in behavior and style with Donald J. Trump who also engineered multiple purported illegal, unethical “mob boss style” actions to obliterate any threats and competition including his guilt with the Stormy Daniels case he also paid to go away but was caught. On January 12, 2018, The Wall Street Journal reported that in October 2016, just before the 2016 United States presidential election, Michael Cohen, lawyer for then-presidential candidate Donald Trump, arranged a payment of \$130,000 to pornographic film actress Stormy Daniels to stop her from disclosing an affair she and Trump allegedly had in 2006 while he was married to his current wife, Melania. On March 30, 2023, a Manhattan grand jury indicted Trump for his alleged role in the scandal. Trump was arraigned in the Manhattan district court on April 4. In only a short period ending in 2023, Trump had accumulated 91 felony charges connected to 4 or 5 ongoing federal and civil investigations and potential trials. (Donald Trump, Wikipedia, January 2024).

McMahon's on-screen persona is also known for his throaty exclamation of "You're fired!", and his "power walk", an exaggerated strut toward the ring, swinging his arms and bobbing his head from side to side in a cocky manner. The idea behind his theme song, "No Chance in Hell", was "He's got the power, the money, and he was pretty much the only game in town”.

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This bravado played out most dangerously in real life during COVID. As a poignant example Trump went on daily during press conferences deciding/not deciding to state to Dr. Anthony Fauci whether he would fire him or not. This was reminiscent of Vince McMahon almost weekly during his shows threatening a wrestler he suddenly had disfavor with “you’re fired”. How did both personalities magically arrive at the same aggressive term to eliminate people? Fauci, who often spoke alongside Trump at briefings about managing the pandemic, said breaking with the former president to maintain his “personal and scientific integrity and fulfill my responsibilities to the American public” sometimes turned into a personal risk. “That I had to disagree publicly with the president of the United States”. The nation’s leading infectious-disease expert, Anthony S. Fauci — a public face of the government’s response to the coronavirus pandemic — shared his concern about the toll on his wife and children from abuse by Trump loyalists. The abuse toward his family was more perturbing, he said. He noted that at least two people are in jail in the United States for “credible” attempts on his life and those of his total family.

In looking at WWE Pro Wrestling and any relationship to the Trump “retribution” strategy, if and when he wins the next election, we need to look at current events and themes for a further understanding. McMahon, the shrewd architect of the WWE, is no longer permitted to manage his empire due to multiple lawsuits brought against him beginning in 1992 by former female employees charging him with sexual harassment to rape. He responded to these allegations by paying off these disgruntled/abused women with corporate money which was illegal and resulted in the Board separating him from his playground of 50 years or more. The WWE board began investigating a \$3 million hush-money settlement that McMahon paid over an alleged affair with a former employee of the company in April 2022. The investigation also revealed other nondisclosure agreements related to misconduct claims by other women in the company against McMahon now totaling \$12 million. McMahon stepped down as CEO and chairman of WWE. He formally announced his retirement on July 22, 2022, only to return six months later. By October 2022, the WWE had disclosed an ever-higher amount of \$20 million in unrecorded payments McMahon made to settle sexual misconduct claims between 2006 and 2022 (World Wrestling Entertainment, Wikipedia, January 2024). McMahon's close friend and former on-screen rival, ex-U.S. president Donald Trump, praised McMahon, stating: "People love this stuff, and it's all because of Vince McMahon and his vision". There appears to be similar behaviors and strategies both men have employed and continue to do.

TRUMP AND MCMAHON PUBLIC PERSONA BUILDING

Pro wrestling is an enterprise built on larger-than-life personalities, brash talk and bold proclamations. Trump has each of those elements at the top of his toolbox. However, the audience didn't see that side of McMahon at first in the 1970's through the end of that century. As an announcer, he blended into the product. He was actually low key and not exciting. Eventually, though, he morphed into the villainous Mr. McMahon, a loud, no-nonsense, power-hungry

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executive. Nothing about the McMahon character is subtle. He yells with veins bulging in his neck. He grins as he puts his foot on his enemy's throat.

And while Trump isn't ordering his underlings to smash anybody with a steel chair, there's an over-the-top nature to his personality that is reminiscent of McMahon's. He holds little back. He's aggressive, unapologetic, and loud, all qualities shared by the onscreen version of McMahon. Trump stretches the truth like a wrestling promoter as well. McMahon has no issue to adding a few inches on one of his giants for the sake of entertainment. Trump does his truth-stretching elsewhere and has been accused of exaggerating his successes, like the height of his buildings and how much money he has.

McMahon's empire brims with hyperbole. The newest big bout is often referred to as the biggest match in WWE history. The company has trotted out wrestlers known as The World's Most Dangerous Man, The World's Largest Athlete and The Eighth Wonder of the World. However, a new world record is set yearly just before the next big show for hype (Vince McMahon, Wikipedia, January 2024).

And although Trump and McMahon sell vastly different products, they both do so at great volume and with a hit-the-audience-over-the-head style. That's why so many critics have referred to Trump as a carnival barker a la P.T. Barnum.

Trump himself is aware of the non-subtlety of his approach. As seen in Slater's *No Such Thing as Over-Exposure*, Trump said, "I believe in doing things big. If you're going to go for it, go for it. Make it the biggest, make it the best." (Slater, 2005). In looking at any WWE production, it's clear that McMahon has the same philosophy. Massive wrestlers battle in massive stadiums with massive video screens hanging above them. Each wrestler has become more than a salesperson. Each has become a vital part of his brand. Trump went beyond buying up buildings to being the face of his hit reality show, *The Apprentice*. McMahon became his company's own best villain. Both of their brands expanded because of their own presence.

This is where the paths of the two workaholics part. McMahon remains busy looking to keep his current kingdom flourishing amid minimal competition. Trump, though, aggressively seeks a new crown, the emperor of edifices eager to broaden his reach. He seeks to be a king who sets the rules he will not legally follow. The election and his kingdom are endless per his boasts.

THE BATTLE OF THE BILLIONAIRES

McMahon and Trump had a wrestling connection as far back as 1984 for the initial WrestleMania. McMahon then challenged Trump to a match at WrestleMania 23 in 2007 billed as 'the battle of the billionaires'. It was a "hair vs. hair match: the loser gets his head shaved. Neither man was

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really going to wrestle, so each one handpicked one superstar to represent him. Trump revealed his representative a week earlier than he was meant to on a Don Imus radio show but couldn't remember his name. It was a rising superstar-Bobby Lashley, a fan favorite and a babyface. Unfortunately, he did not know the name of his meal ticket. So, he ended up settling with 'a black gentleman who happens to be the strongest man he had ever seen' he claimed in the hype. But it would be McMahon who selected his wrestler Umaga, depicted as a destructive savage (Donald Trump, Wikipedia, January 2024) (Vince McMahon, Wikipedia, January 2024). As the weeks wore on, the story got more and more interesting. They decided the loser of the match would have to have his hair shaved off, and Stone-Cold Steve Austin was installed as the special guest referee. The match had much mainstream attention, especially the prospect of Trump losing his trademark hair. Umaga did lose the Battle of the Billionaires' hair versus hair match' and caused McMahon to get his head shaved. No way Trump was going to part with his now famous perfect hair which he still claims is all his. In this spectator sport, Trump, switched roles using a juxtaposition where he now became the hero and McMahon the bully. He continues to place the spotlight on legitimate governmental institutions investigating him for potential crimes that he targets as "the bad guys" out to get him as he is always innocent. This role reversal has worked well for him in entertainment and career. Now he's peddling it in politics.

Finally, in 2013, Trump took his place in WWE's Hall of Fame. He resides in the celebrity wing with questionable names like Pete Rose, Snoop Dogg, and Mike Tyson. Trump did say during his speech that evening he considered it a 'major honor' and one of the best of his career. It seems even he had no idea what was to come. It is important to note that his popularity was dropping quickly and as usual he needed another PR gimmick to be on the big screen of TV as he was for years on the front page of NY Post. Donald Trump flirted with presidential runs in 1988, 2000, 2004, 2008 and 2012. He also teased about running for governor of New York in 2006. He did the WWE fiasco in 2007 (Donald Trump, Wikipedia, January 2024). Trump never actually ran for office until he decided in 2011 that Barack Obama had to be replaced and by him. He managed to draw a lot of attention to himself by pretending to be interested in running for office but being screwed over. He made it a reality in 2015. This appeared to be a major aspect of his part of his brand building.

RELIVING WORLD WAR TWO IN THE RING

Vince McMahon is a creative businessman who has shrewdly integrated politics and world events into his characters and business. Trump has also introjected the same stylistics into his policies and politics. Interestingly, as Trump was revving up the "fascist platform" for a 2024 run, McMahon featured a new group a year ago, "The Imperium" featuring two partners from Germany and one from Italy, their style and theatrical stance(roles) are clearly "Nazi," coincidentally two of America's enemies circa WW II. Two of the wrestlers even do the famous and disgraced "goose step" in the ring during the matches. The goose step was intended during WW II to convey the impression that the soldier was made of iron to the followers. The feet are slammed down in unison creating an

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impressive crash and a sharp line of legs. It suggests that these soldiers are immaculately disciplined and feel no pain. It was initially performed for Hitler and Mussolini to connote total followership. McMahon somehow transmitted it to his ring of wrestling at the same time of Trump's fascist proclamations. As an academic I rarely believe in coincidences.

While it's a show, it illuminates a current and very troubling trend projected by McMahon and echoed by Trump with his affection and admiration for "anarchy oriented" leaders in Hungary-Argentina-Korea-China and always, Russia. His romance with Fascism and Nazism and anti-anyone not pure US white is growing as is his followers. During this short time and intense spotlighting on Nazi-type wrestlers the number of antisemitic incidents across the US and worldwide increased exponentially. This was no coincidence as there are few coincidences in pro wrestling. Remember his recent comment. "Hitler Did a Lot of Good Things"! (Donald Trump, Wikipedia, January 2024), There is no coincidence he refers to his non-believers as "vermin" a popular term used by Adolph Hitler. In public appearances Trump had been doubling down on flaming rhetoric by referring to "illegal immigrants are poisoning the blood of our nation". This statement was directly taken from the 1939 book *Mein Kampf* (which means "My Struggle") authored by Adolf Hitler which was part autobiography and part political treatise. *Mein Kampf* promoted the key components of Nazism: rabid antisemitism, a racist world view, and an aggressive foreign policy geared to gaining *Lebensraum* (living space) in eastern Europe. Hitler began writing *Mein Kampf* in 1924 in Landsberg prison, following his conviction for high treason for attempting to overthrow the German republic in November 1923 (Adolf Hitler, Wikipedia, January 2024). Although his coup failed, Hitler used his trial as a pulpit to spread Nazi propaganda and his political ambitions very similar to the Trump tactics echoed almost daily by Trump for his acolytes.

McMahon who demands his employees refer to him as the Boss and Mr. McMahon projects an appearance of never considering running a democratic ship. He thrives on autocratic outbursts where, in early years his pro wrestling stable, selected employees even had to get on their knees and lick his boots and his famous series "kiss my butt" that was televised which was dehumanizing to most people except to the followers of these two demagogues who enjoyed the dehumanization of anything/anyone normal. Trump also praises these types of theatrical tactics as he often refers to Vladimir Putin as one of his models often labelled as an enemy of Democracy.

Trump "telegraphs his punches" (an old boxing term) of what he will do and when he will do it. He just needs to win at any expense including voter fraud-threatening election workers-obstruction-conspiracy- concentration camps again. Trump always says what he's going to do. He believes if he tells you he can't be implicated in anything criminal. He intends to marginalize the DOJ and FBI with his political appointees and make the military of the US his personal "retribution force" "to be able to pay back his foes and enemies of the state including anyone who ran against him for office. This is the quintessential model of Russian politics. Maya Angelou the American

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memoirist, poet, and civil rights activist famous quote “When someone shows you who they are, believe them the first time”(Maya Angelou, Wikipedia 2024). Interestingly in pro wrestling interviews before the big events the bad guys (heels) scream at their baby face opponent of what they will do to them if and when the match is scheduled like-kidnapping relatives-permanent injury or permanent retirement. The babyfaces listen and tell the aggressor that they will do their talking in the ring. The good guys don’t seem as exciting as the bad guys somehow. Trump does the same at rallies or special interviews, But Biden chooses to be calm, rational and speak of accomplishments and not retribution. But Trump and the GOP position him as “weak”. He acts like a President not a mobster. How will this match play out in the public arena?

CONTRASTING BOTH PARTIES AND CANDIDATES- THE MATCH OF THE NEAR FUTURE

Let us examine both parties starting with the Democrats and their foundations. The party's traditional coalition has consisted of the working class, Catholics, mainline Protestants, Jews, Black people, Hispanics, intellectuals, and organized labor since the time of the New Deal. Its philosophy of modern American liberalism blends civil liberty and social equality with support for a mixed capitalist economy. On social issues, it advocates for the continued legality of abortion, the legalization of marijuana, and LGBTQ rights. On economic issues, it favors universal healthcare coverage, universal childcare, paid sick leave, protectionism, and supporting unions. During the presidency of Joe Biden, the GOP has shifted drastically towards embracing a muscular, internationalist, and interventionist foreign policy, with the Democratic Party supporting large-scale military aid to Israel and Ukraine in their respective conflicts (Democratic Party, Wikipedia, January 2024).

A brief sketch of Joe Biden helps clarify this muddle. He decided to run for the US Senate in 1972 in Delaware. Biden defeated a Republican incumbent to become the junior U.S. senator from Delaware in 1972. He was the only Democrat willing to mount this challenge and, with minimal campaign funds, he was thought to have no chance of winning. He won but then the bottom dropped out. A few weeks after Biden was elected senator, his wife Neilia and one-year-old daughter Naomi were killed in an automobile accident while Christmas shopping in Delaware on December 18, 1972. Neilia’s station wagon was hit by a semi-trailer truck as she pulled out from an intersection. Their sons Beau (aged 3) and Hunter (aged 2) had been in the car and were taken to the hospital with non-life-threatening injuries. Biden considered resigning to care for them, but Senate Majority Leader Mike Mansfield persuaded him not to. At age 30, he was the seventh youngest senator in U.S. history (Joe Biden, Wikipedia, January 2024).

To see and take care of his damaged sons both emotionally and physically, Biden traveled by train between his Delaware home and D.C.—74 minutes each way—and maintained this habit throughout his 36 years in the Senate until being selected by Barack Obama as his running mate

in 2008. Most senators had full-time residences in Washington, but Joe Biden was as different from them as Donald Trump was an anomaly to most everyone in Washington in general and to Biden in particular. Trump has often said he began his career with "a small loan of one million dollars" from his father and that he had to pay it back with interest. He was a millionaire by age eight, borrowed at least \$60 million from his father, largely failed to repay those loans, and received another \$413 million (2018 dollars adjusted for inflation) from his father's company. Contrary to his claims of financial health and business acumen, Trump's tax returns from 1985 to 1994 show net losses totaling \$1.17 billion (Donald Trump, Wikipedia, January 2024). The losses were higher than those of almost every other American taxpayer. However, he continues to deny these researchable facts to today. This is his MO.

While Biden travelled on Amtrak, Trump projected his personal wealth by often travelling during his campaign using his huge aircraft fleet. Trump Force One (a Boeing 757) is a nickname, coined to sound analogous to Air Force One prior to and after his presidency. The name was in use during his presidential campaign of 2016. Trump also owns a Cessna jet, which was reportedly worth \$15.3 million when it was new and had a resale value of \$3.2 million in 2016. Collectively, Trump's fleet, comprised of two airplanes and one helicopter, is valued at \$15 million. Not only are their politics different, but their public persona is also at opposite ends of the continuum.

UPDATING THE PARTIES AND THE BIG-BIG MATCH

A freeze-dried snapshot of the Republicans can be briefly described by the following. The 1980 election of Ronald Reagan realigned national politics, bringing together advocates of free-market economics, social conservatives, and Cold War foreign policy hawks under the Republican banner. George W. Bush oversaw the response to the September 11 attacks and the Iraq War. These were traditional Republican positions until Donald Trump decided to rewrite the playbook to enhance his own needs and wants. Since 2008, Republicans have faced intense factionalism within their own ranks. As of the 2020s, the party derives its strongest support from rural voters, evangelical Christians, men, senior citizens, and white voters without college degrees. Its platform on social issues calls for significantly restricting the legality of abortion, prohibiting non-medical cannabis, loosening gun laws, and overturning the legality of same-sex marriage. On economic issues, the Republican Party supports a laissez-faire economic system, deregulation, and increased military spending, while opposing labor unions and universal health care (Republican Party, Wikipedia, January 2024). Here is where former President Trump and the party he runs under the banner separate. Trump has no platform or policies...his *raison d'être* is to win at any costs and stay out of jail for the next 5 years. He is desperate and the GOP cannot reign him in.

The MAGA Trumpers report card during his 2016-2020 tenure illuminates they accomplished little for America except excessive tax reductions for the top 1% of his close donors and friends and building a still unfinished promised wall in 2015. His famous words coming down his escalator in

2015 now almost tripled in intensity were: “When Mexico sends its people (immigrants), they’re not sending their best. They are sending people that have lots of problems, and they’re bringing those problems with us. They are bringing drugs, they’re bringing crime, they’re rapists. And some, I assume, are good people” (Donald Trump, Wikipedia, January 2024). For Heather Haddon, then a political reporter at the Wall Street Journal, one of the surprises was that Trump had finally done it. He told all his followers what he believed they wanted to hear, and he was their voice and savior. As for the event itself, Haddon remembers there being an “almost pro-wrestling “tone to the announcement (Heather Haddon, Wall Street Journal, April 2016). His base believes he will magically give them personally what they have never achieved in their lifetime and a vote for him is a vote out of poverty. To be clear, to date the former president has been charged to the tune of 91 felony counts across numerous criminal cases. In five states: New York, Florida, Colorado, Georgia, and Washington DC for criminal acts from voter fraud, obstruction of US justice system, multiple sexual allegations. But these deadly charges for almost anyone else running for office are like a duck-they all roll off the back of this “victim” since everything per him has been rigged against him even before he ran in 2015 via the “deep state” and DOJ and FBI and of course, the Democrats as well as RINOS who turned against him.

THE TRUMP MYSTIQUE

We need to briefly examine the appeal of Donald Trump the New York real estate magnate and TV personality concerning his popularity with his base that are most interestingly from red states that historically despised “loud mouthed” New Yorkers like Trump. He is not reluctant to smash the red-white & blue model we all thought impervious to someone running a campaign on being an anarchist. What is it about anarchy that he embraces so warmly? To start with it is a state of lawlessness or political disorder due to the absence of governmental authority. Also, to be considered a utopian society of individuals who enjoy complete freedom without government and ultimately this absence of order leads to disorder. Laws that are not carried into effect, authorities without force and despised, crime unpunished, property attacked, the safety of the individual violated, the morality of the people corrupted, no constitution, no government, and no justice. These are the basic features of anarchy. Hold it: the very strong leader then steps up and takes over completely as he wishes to be like a king. This is what the US ran from in 1776.

Trump appears to be luring his followers like communistic and fascist countries a la Putin to something akin to these sentiments: “I know what you have been screwed out of and I will restore your dignity that you have lost to those who are not pure white like you and me”. He promises he will make it easy on them by making all decisions for them to make their lives much, much better than with the left wingers in charge who love immigrants that he and his followers need to eliminate. The reward is they can sit back and depend on him totally to make their lives what they really want as he knows them better than they do themselves. He reminds them that they have been at the bottom rung of the ladder since the Civil War and with him in charge the “welfare queens”

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he currently refers to in states with significant black voters will be penalized as they should have been over 160 years ago. And it is not too late to catch up and overtake the rigged lefty system if he does it for them. The price for this magical kingdom is their vote and unfortunately, their freedom if he succeeds. The result of this is they can sit back and trust him since they will be “psychologically and economically compensated” as Putin and other anarchists and tyrannists do if they continue to vote for him as both Trump and Putin amass their own personal fortunes and the masses get their basic needs fulfilled and lower levels of subsistence without doing much more. This is an extremely attractive “social contract”. How do the reality-based Democrats (boring opponents in pro wrestling) fracture this “fantasy crystal ball”? This is the “magic act” Trump has been able to perform... how did someone who personified 80’s decadence position themselves amongst the “common man: from 2015 to ensnare their loyalty? In any normal context, he would be viewed as the enemy, but he has been able to position himself to fight for them. That is the challenge.

SOME FINAL THOUGHTS

As previously described, in professional wrestling, a babyface is a heroic, "good guy" or "fan favorite" wrestler, booked (scripted) by the promotion with the aim of being cheered by fans. They are portrayed as heroes relative to the heel wrestlers, who are analogous to the villains. Traditionally, babyface characters wrestle within the rules and avoid cheating while behaving courteously towards the referee and the audience. In the ring, they are expected to abide by the rules and win matches by their own skill rather than by cheating, outside interference, etc. Because heel wrestlers take little issues with using such tactics, the babyface enters many matches already at a disadvantage to the heel. But how does this explain Biden’s next and crucial strategic move to win this match currently appearing to be flawed?

Trump... Trump... Trump... but not much is said in this article about Joe Biden and the Democrats. Why not? In terms of balanced writing this does not seem fair. However, not much is fair in politics and wrestling. Well, one of the entertainment reasons which affects both politics and pro wrestling is that Donald Trump is personally and strategically controversial and a natural villain of which he is proud. So is Vince McMahon who was proud way back from the entertaining middle of the road owner of the earlier editions of the show to being a “toxic bad boss” and “Executive Villian.” Biden is still a “baby face” naturally and democratically as he and the party (not perfect by any means) somehow seek to appear so reasonable and willing to always compromise at any expense when Trump is proud to be unreasonable and takes no hostages. This constant PR barrage is very entertaining and garners high TV ratings. Will it convert to high electoral numbers and the prize that goes with it? So, who will win this PR “rassling-political battle”? One of the problems is that the very reasonable Democrats believe in rational debate and struggling to “work across the aisle” with the other party that has zero interest in cooperation. It is interested in winning at any cost no matter how it’s done legally or illegally as long as they stay in power. The Dems are playing whiffle

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ball similar to checkers and the GOP are playing hard ball similar to 3-D chess and throwing at your head since the umpire a la wrestling will look the other way as most are Trumpers in this current setting. This is a no-win, unless the Democratic party starts understanding and implementing mortal combat rules which is how successful dirty wrestlers are and win! They are not used to this since intellectual debate is more comfortable for them. They may slip on their own banana peel and lose since it takes two to tango and the MAGA group is dancing to another tune.

This is where the Joe Biden persona and impact on the next election comes under the microscope. He just doesn't make flaming outrageous headlines like Trump that we are conditioned to listen to and even eagerly watch even more (without admitting it) no matter how we will vote next year. Trump with his "The Apprentice" training and flamboyant character gets people excited to even see more of this asymmetrical rhetoric that many people say in public to look more normalized that they do not support him but in their guts may admire. Make no mistake, Trump has tapped into something growing in America that may have been here for many years where there is a fondness for "strongmen" who are dictatorial. He has been able to normalize this rhetoric for his followers. Remember there are no return match clauses in this political social contract as there are in pro wrestling. The ending of this serious "soap opera" will be permanent.

In pro wrestling there are several outcomes to every match: a clean victory where the referee counts 1-2-3 when one wrestler pins another's shoulders to the mat. Then there is another where one submits due to a special hold so painful, they give up. Now it is getting a bit foggier. There can be a draw where the time limit is exhausted and no declared winner. This usually requires a return bout for the audience to see if their favorite can pull it off another time. Also, there can be a "no contest" verdict when both wrestlers are out of control that the referee cannot maintain order in the ring and orders the timekeeper to ring the bell and stop the action, which usually doesn't happen. In this scenario there is no winner nor loser. When all is quiet a surprise announcement previewing the return match for a clean verdict, whatever that means in pro wrestling is the usual modus operandi. This outcome is closer to election reality.

One more outcome: disqualification. If one wrestler violates the referee's count of up to 5 and does not release his opponent, then he is disqualified. This is usually unsportsmanlike conduct and flagrant misconduct or even a breach of the referees' instructions. The opponent already overly abused is declared the winner but it's not a clean victory and usually a return match is scheduled for the fans to see if their favorite can emerge a clean winner (Professional Wrestling, Wikipedia, January 2024). As 2023 ended, in Colorado the State Supreme Court had declared Donald Trump to be disqualified from being placed on the election slate. We can see the multiple problems and potential scenarios that have been brought about with no winner and more enigmas yet to be decided. However, the GOP side of the aisle is screaming for this decision to be thrown out and let the match continue with their fan favorite who committed several alleged criminal infractions leading the Colorado legislature to render this decision. Maine has followed suit in declaring his

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candidacy to be illegitimate for similar reasons as Colorado and to have him removed from the next election ballot. To date approximately 16 other states have seriously entertained this potential action to have Donald Trump removed from the ballot. So, the rules for inclusion will now be viewed as “flawed rules” since the favorite “bad guy” needs to still be in the running and on the ballot no matter what Article 14 of the US Constitution stated as a penalty leading to this major unprecedented move. In pro wrestling there are no rules when the “heel” does what he wants to, and this leads to a return match and more revenue for the promoters. However, in the real world of politics (whatever that is) there are no automatic return matches even though Trump screamed for this after his 2020 loss. He used a segway directly to pro wrestling which is believed to be fixed and claimed the election was rigged! In wrestling this is almost expected. In politics it could be a disaster for democracy and the US with Trump boasting if he wins, he never leaves office and no use for elections under that autocratic new world order.

So, who will win this real-life match? Will there be a clean victory or interference from a third party? Remember, unlike wrestling, there will not be a return match clause for the next PPV. There will not be another show or chance to maintain democracy as we know it...we only have one shot at it in 2024. It is a winner takes all situation.

As a kid the story of the Tortoise and the Hare always intrigued me. Many of us may remember that the story concerns a Hare who ridicules a slow-moving Tortoise. There are political characters in the cast. Tired of the Hare’s (Trump) arrogant behavior, the Tortoise (Biden) challenges him to a race. The hare soon leaves the Tortoise behind and, confident of winning, takes a nap midway through the race. The Tortoise continued to move very slowly but without stopping and finally won the race. The moral of the story is that you can be more successful by doing things slowly and steadily than by acting quickly and carelessly. Do not be arrogant. The Hare (Trump) was overwhelmingly cocky. To an extent, it is understandable. Hares are naturally fast, and Tortoises (Biden) are naturally slow and moreover is he not “too old “to run for President per Trumps attacks? The Hare had this in the bag until something unexpected happened. He cried out victory publicly before the official event (the election) was over and votes were counted to proclaim the winner. Of course, this story highlights that no amount of natural advantage will beat consistency. This race and match require audience participation-the voters. But it was only a story.

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